

DiSSCo related output

This template collects the required metadata to reference the official Deliverables and Milestones of DiSSCo-related projects. More information on the mandatory and conditionally mandatory fields can be found in the supporting document 'Metadata for DiSSCo Knowledge base' that is shared among work package leads, and in Teamwork > Files. A short explanatory text is given for all metadata fields, thus allowing easy entry of the required information. If there are any questions, please contact us at info@dissco.eu.

Title

DPP WP4 MS4.3 "Revenue stream based on identified partnerships"

Author(s)

Michel GUIRAUD (MNHN)
Salomé LANDEL (MNHN)
François DUSOULIER (MNHN)
Eva PEREZ (MNHN)
Katharine WORLEY (MNHN)
Eva ALONSO (Naturalis)

Identifier of the author(s)

0000-0003-3125-8947 - Michel GUIRAUD (MNHN)
0000-0001-5360-5693 - Salomé LANDEL (MNHN)
0000-0001-9062-5239 - François DUSOULIER (MNHN)
0000-0002-5752-5903 - Eva PEREZ (MNHN)
0000-0003-2377-6840 - Katharine WORLEY (MNHN)
0000-0001-5336-9723 - Eva ALONSO (Naturalis)

Affiliation

Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle

Contributors

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS)
Agentschap Planetarium Meise
Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung (SGN)
National History Museum (NHM)
Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF)
Naturalis

Publisher

Michel GUIRAUD (MNHN)

Identifier of the publisher

0000-0003-3125-8947 - Michel GUIRAUD (MNHN)

Resource ID

Publication year

2021

Related identifiers

Is it the first time you submit this outcome?

Yes

Creation date

01/09/2021

Version

1

Citation

Guiraud M., (et al.). 2021 Milestone report MS 4.3 "Revenue stream based on identified partnerships".

Abstract

This milestone 4.3 considers possible public / governmental revenue streams for the Distributed System of Scientific Collections Research Infrastructure (DiSSCo-RI) and identifies key partnerships that will ensure a suitable and economically sustainable model for national contributions to the RI. It will look at the main

financial challenges of creating a sustainable DiSSCo, taking into consideration DiSSCo's unique position within the taxonomy and open data landscapes. A key consideration in this milestone is the need for financial contributions to DiSSCo to cover its central activity: the production of data, an activity which should allow the research infrastructure to reach a broader user group and attract increased investment. It will also analyse the existing ESFRI landscape and contribution models in order to ascertain to what extent these models could be applicable, or not, in the creation of the DiSSCo research infrastructure. This milestone is drafted in close collaboration with DPP WP7 (Governance, Policy and Legal framework – Task 7.1).

Content keywords

financial

Project reference

DiSSCo Prepare (GA-871043)

WP number

WP4

Project output

Milestone report

Deliverable/milestone number

4.3

Dissemination level

Public

Rights

Free access

License

Attribution 4.0
International (CC BY
4.0)

Resource type

Text

Format

PDF

Funding**Programme**

H2020-INFRADEV-
2019-2

Contact email

katharine.worley@m
nhn.fr

National contributions to the DiSSCo RI

DiSSCo Prepare WP4 – Milestone 4.3 Revenue stream based on identified partnerships

Work package leader: Michel GUIRAUD (MNHN)

Task leader: Muséum national d'histoire naturelle (MNHN)

Authors: Katharine WORLEY, Salomé LANDEL, Michel GUIRAUD, François DUSOULIER, Eva PEREZ

Contributors: Eva ALONSO, Dimitris KOUREAS (**Naturalis**); Ana CASINO (**CETAF**);
Patricia MERGEN, Frederik LELIAERT
Carole PALECO, Serge SCORY, Jonathan BRECKO, Patrick SEMAL (**IRSNB**); Helen
HARDY, Laurence LIVERMORE, Lisa FRENCH (**NHM**)

Abstract

This milestone 4.3 considers possible public / governmental revenue streams for the Distributed System of Scientific Collections Research Infrastructure (DiSSCo-RI) and identifies key partnerships that will ensure a suitable and economically sustainable model for national contributions to the RI. It will look at the main financial challenges of creating a sustainable DiSSCo, taking into consideration DiSSCo's unique position within the taxonomy and open data landscapes. A key consideration in this milestone is the need for financial contributions to DiSSCo to cover its central activity: the production of data, an activity which should allow the research infrastructure to reach a broader user group and attract increased investment. It will also analyse the existing ESFRI landscape and contribution models in order to ascertain to what extent these models could be applicable, or not, in the creation of the DiSSCo research infrastructure. This milestone is drafted in close collaboration with DPP WP7 (Governance, Policy and Legal framework – Task 7.1).

Key words

National contributions, contribution model, benchmarking, DiSSCo, service revenue, project revenue, partnerships, Natural Science Collections

H2020-INFRADEV-2019-2
Grant Agreement No 871043

INDEX

- 1. Introduction..... 4
 - 1.1 Defining revenue streams 4
- 2. Using revenue streams to finance data production 5
 - 2.1 DiSSCo added value 6
 - 2.2 Revenue creation through access to DiSSCo services 7
- 3. Benchmarking contribution models for ESFRI Research Infrastructures 9
- 4. Possible contribution models for the DiSSCo RI..... 14
- 5. Conclusion and next steps..... 15
- 6. References..... 16

1. Introduction

During the construction and operational phases of DiSSCo, and following the wrapping-up of the EU-funded DiSSCo Prepare project (DPP) in early 2023, the research infrastructure will be reliant on stable and guaranteed income from European partners – as well as possible international public funding from governments outside the EU – to ensure the provision of services and to cement its position as a competitive RI within the European landscape. Financial commitments from national governments are likely to form the backbone of DiSSCo revenue, and agreements will need to be implemented to consolidate this.

This milestone aims to establish the key partnerships of the DiSSCo contribution model and is a first step in considering the future funding landscape. The suggestions and assumptions offered in this milestone in no way constitute final decisions, and developments within other DiSSCo Prepare work packages will most likely influence future discussions that have an impact on this task. Namely, DPP Task 7.1 is considering suitable governance models for DiSSCo and these discussions will have a direct impact on the evolution of income partnerships, for example in the levels of representation of funding bodies within the governance structure. There are also links with Task 8.3 in the establishment of strategic partnerships and within Task 2.3, seeking to build a strategic map that establishes the alignment between HR policy and the strategic objectives of DiSSCo.

A key consideration underlying the economic sustainability of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure focusses on its capacity to produce data, not only to exploit it. As a result of this, the research infrastructure will increase the availability of knowledge, opening up access to identification, expertise and tools. The challenge of operating an economically sustainable research infrastructure in the age of open data is to ensure that funding partnerships provide sufficient medium- to long-term financial commitment to make it possible for DiSSCo to embark on costly knowledge production programmes which will create valuable resources for the DiSSCo community (e.g. scientific community and the general public).

1.1 Defining revenue streams

The DiSSCo contribution model adheres to the assumption that data must be “free at the point of use” and will work in alignment with FAIR data principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that DiSSCo will not generate revenue from providing access to data (transaction-based revenue).

Conversely, access to services, which enable the exploitation of data, will have a cost to the user: indeed, this will form the basis of the DiSSCo business model. Nevertheless, existing data will remain free at the point of use, regardless of the user group. Once the data has been created (whether through a paid production initiative or otherwise), access to it is free. The production of data is likely to be a primary expense for the infrastructure: Section 2 will take a closer look at the cost of data production.

Access to services will therefore generate some service revenue, however this could be channelled directly to DiSSCo operators and therefore is unlikely to constitute a revenue stream for the DiSSCo Central hub. (This is assuming the DiSSCo Central hub does not provide core services. If it does, this funding model would need to be reconsidered.) As noted in Milestone 8.4, it is currently unclear where the boundaries will be between the DiSSCo Central hub and institutional responsibilities. One assumption could be for some services to be billed at the end of use (see Section 2).

DiSSCo is also likely to generate some income through project revenue. European funded projects, like SYNTHESIS+, have set a promising precedent for the availability and popularity of this funding for transnational and virtual access and it is possible to imagine that, once operational, DiSSCo will be central to the coordination of similar projects within the scientific program portfolio. This is dependent on European Commission project calls and the suitability of these calls within the remit of DiSSCo. As this milestone will aim to demonstrate, revenue from EU projects will be an important, albeit unpredictable, source of revenue for the RI.

Crucially, to lay the foundations of a sustainable infrastructure, DiSSCo will require a predictable source of recurring revenue in the form of national contributions. Following the vote in favour of an ERIC legal framework at the DiSSCo General Assembly on 11 June 2021, this status will become a working hypothesis for future discussions. Therefore, national contributions should become the main source of revenue for DiSSCo-ERIC. Section 3 of this milestone will study how established ERICs manage these national contributions and consider how national partnerships could be integrated into a DiSSCo-specific model.

As this milestone will seek to explore, one particularity of contributions to research infrastructure is the assumption that in-kind contributions will play a more or less important role in national funding. This may include contributions in the form of staff time and resources, particularly but not only from the host country, and/or contributions from national nodes. These partnerships will be crucial in assuring collaboration and common targets amongst all partners in the research infrastructure and assigning value to in-kind contributions will be a key challenge in the elaboration of the contribution model. The importance of the role of these contributions should not be underestimated, “the discussion on the cost of coordination, being in cash, tends to overtake the fact that the in-kind investment and contributions are much bigger” (Rizzuto *et al*).

Taking these elements into consideration, the following sections aim to explore the fundamental elements of the future DiSSCo contribution model.

2. Using revenue streams to finance data production

The hypothesis underpinning the revenue needs of DiSSCo is that the DiSSCo economic model is reliant on the production of data. According to the CERIC-ERIC RAMIRI study (Rizzuto *et al.*), the success of a research infrastructure “is not measured by net income but by knowledge production and by its impact on public knowledge (non-economic, and mainly without income)”. A sort of dichotomy is apparent in this statement, insofar as revenue (the subject of this milestone) is essential for the smooth functioning of the RI but is not a marker of its success. Rather, the production of knowledge is a measurement of

the health of the RI, and a marker of its intellectual value. It is also what will allow the RI to expand its user group and find new investment, therefore increasing its economic sustainability. Because of this, funding streams should be tailored to facilitate the production of data, finance the competencies needed in its production, and ensure efficient and value-generating exploitation.

2.1 DiSSCo added value

If knowledge and data production is a key marker of success for DiSSCo, the RI should facilitate and implement this in as many ways as possible, by committing a large part of its revenue to production. One way of exploring visually the input and output of DiSSCo is to consider a possible business model, established as part of this milestone (Figure 1).

Figure 1: possible DiSSCo business model

From this business model it is possible to show how funding channelled in to the DiSSCo infrastructure creates both financially and non-financially quantifiable outputs. These could become Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) once the research infrastructure becomes fully operational. The purpose of this diagram is to show how revenue (from private industry, EU calls, public national funds and policy advisory bodies (like the European Environment Agency)) will be used by DiSSCo, demonstrating the financial outputs and the value generated through these activities. If DiSSCo is in a healthier financial situation and therefore able to produce data which will prove useful for a broad range of projects and

sectors, it is more likely to attract new partnerships and therefore receive greater funding (thus reducing the burden on national funders). Likewise, the value created within DiSSCo, such as collaborative tools developed as a result of a variety of partnerships, or new scientific expertise, will continue to attract users who wish to access DiSSCo resources.

2.2 Revenue creation through access to DiSSCo services

Looking to the future of DiSSCo services, we should consider how DiSSCo institutions will finance the production of data. As the European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures states, when considering revenue of RIs, “acknowledging a variety of financing models, costs need to be covered and fees for Access, to the extent found necessary, should contribute to the financial sustainability of the Research Infrastructure”.

As part of this milestone, and in order to consider the economic sustainability of DiSSCo, we have established three possible access channels which are funded by three different revenue streams. These are:

- Individual physical access through the ELViS access portal (Fig. 2)
- Access managed by the DiSSCo central hub within the remit of an EU-funded programme (Fig.2)
- DiSSCo operators take part in government-funded mass-digitisation project (Fig. 3)

1. Passive Access:

- Direct connection through ELViS
- No funding through DiSSCo

2. EU Programme (eg. Synthesys)

- Allocations of funds through DiSSCo Hub

Figure 2: DiSSCo access channels

One option in the first scenario would be for users to bypass the DiSSCo Central hub and liaise directly with the DiSSCo operator, contacting them through the ELViS access portal (<https://elvis.dissco.eu/welcome>). A future consideration for DiSSCo is the invoicing of this service: one possibility is for this to be managed entirely by the operator. However, for efficient financial

management and coordination, the general consensus is that all financial management of the RI should go through the central hub.

In the second model, the DiSSCo Central hub plays a coordination role, managing the application selection panel, supervising ELViS, and coordinating the feasibility assessment, which is likely to be carried out by DiSSCo institutions and CETAF. This assessment will determine the suitability of the proposal and the capacity of DiSSCo operators to fulfill the project objectives. The transnational and virtual access (TA and VA) project SYNTHESYS+ sets the precedent for this. In this scenario, DiSSCo operators receive, often as linked third parties, a portion of the project funding. Additionally, project funding may go towards human resources (HR) costs in the central hub.

Finally, a government-funded mass-digitisation programme (Fig. 3) would be an innovative way to increase DiSSCo resources and create value within the collections. This kind of initiative would be pioneering insofar as it would need to convince governments to invest money in DiSSCo programmes which would provide a return on their investment, namely through scientific progress which will benefit numerous sectors, and therefore acquire money from different ministries (such as Health, Culture, Environment, etc.) whose interests would be represented. By doing this, DiSSCo increases its partnerships and funding opportunities. Data remains free at the point of access to the user, with the possibility of a temporary data embargo if needed, and DiSSCo can greatly diversify and increase its capacity for data production.

3. Government-funded programme

Figure 3: DiSSCo access through government-funded programme

The three processes outlined above will necessitate in-kind contributions from institutions, cash from governments and EU overheads to fund human resources within the central hub and additional cash from governments to finance the IT office.

The location of the IT infrastructure should be carefully considered, as its site will determine the amount of resources required by the DiSSCo central hub. Purchasing power parity of the country hosting the IT infrastructure will need to be taken into consideration.

3. Benchmarking contribution models for ESFRI Research Infrastructures

Following discussions at WP4-level, we now know that revenue streams are needed to fund data production and that government-funded mass digitisation programmes could be an innovative way of generating additional revenue. Assuming that DiSSCo will be an ERIC, the contribution model will be partially described in the statutes.

In order to better understand the contribution models available to the DiSSCo RI, DPP WP7 partners carried out a series of interviews with research infrastructures to learn more about existing contribution mechanisms for ERICs, which formed part of a wider knowledge-gathering exercise on the governance and structuring of RIs. Directors from the ERICs BBMRI, EPOS, CLARIN, ELI and DARIAH participated in the interviews. The following questions related to the contribution model:

- How did you set the level of core services in relation to the contribution?
- What variables form the basis of the Member States' financial contributions to your RI?
- From your experience, what are the decisions/actions to avoid when building a governance model for a future ERIC?

The responses demonstrated a variety of different approaches: in-kind contributions are of significant weight at DARIAH but less so at BBMRI, for example; and EPOS stressed the importance of improving sustainability of the RI by increasing visibility and leading thematic national priorities. BBMRI and DARIAH advised that the contribution model should be flexible, simple and easily adjustable. The feasibility of this flexibility within DiSSCo will need to be carefully considered: if DiSSCo is to adopt a 5-year data production plan, this could affect the degree of adjustability afforded to the contribution model.

As a continuation of the work carried out by WP7, WP4 leaders MNHN carried out a benchmarking exercise to compare contributions to research infrastructures which featured as landmarks in the 2018 ESFRI Roadmap (Hrušák *et al*). The aim of the exercise was to establish any trends in contribution models that could be pertinent to DiSSCo. Work done by colleagues from the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS), who carried out a comparative study of the national contribution models for the research infrastructures that Belgium participates in, was a valuable resource for this task (document available [here](#)).

In order to carry out the exercise, 16 research infrastructures have been selected, representing the categories Energy (1), Environment (5), Health and Food (6) and Social and Cultural innovation (4). It is important to note that the findings of this benchmarking exercise were limited to information publicly available on the internet. **Whilst the study group was able to access the statutes of all RIs involved in the study, some information was not readily available.**

By comparing the number of members (member countries, excluding observers), the exercise highlighted two possible study groups: RIs with 5-9 members and RIs with 12-28 members. The benchmarking exercise compared the difference in the number of members during the preparatory phase and the operational phase, in an effort to estimate how DiSSCo membership may change (Fig. 4), taking into considering that 21 countries signed the DiSSCo Memorandum of Understanding. 44% of RIs recorded a rise in membership, and 50% a fall, with 6% recording no change. For the purpose of this study, it is possible to imagine that DiSSCo, once operational, will be part of this second group of RIs.

Figure 4: percentage of RIs which lost or gained members between preparatory and operational phases

The exercise came up with a list of the main variables within national contribution models. These were:

- Host country has a higher contribution
- GDP per capita
- Overall GDP
- Contribution grows with time (according to inflation but not always)
- Depends on the number of members/observers
- Fixed and variable amounts
- In-kind and cash contributions
- Number of researchers in the scientific domain of the ERIC
- Not possible to pay more than 25% of the final budget
- Entrance fees
- Exit contributions

The information gathered demonstrated that the revenue and expenditure of each RI did not have a strong correlation with the number of members, but that infrastructures could be divided into three groups corresponding to their level of annual revenue, (less than 1 million euros, between 1-3 million euros and greater than 3 million euros), and the majority of RIs fell within the middle category (Fig. 5).

Whilst there is a slight trend showing the greater the number of members, the greater the total revenue, this is not always the case (take ECRIN as an example).

Figure 5: ERIC resources and expenditure

The study also looked at ERIC income broken down into revenue streams and revealed two key sources of income as national cash contributions and research projects (Fig. 6). Due to the amount of information available it was difficult to assess transaction-based revenue and in-kind contributions.

Figure 6: ERIC resources

Finally, one partnership not yet considered in this milestone is the relationship between the DiSSCo RI and the host country, assuming that a host premium contribution will participate in a more or less significant way to the revenue of the RI. Whilst the location of the DiSSCo Central hub is not yet being

formally discussed, this study tried to determine if a correlation could be established between the location of the hub and the amount of revenue received. The benchmarking exercise studied the location of the central hubs of the 16 RIs, aiming to gain an understanding of the total member contributions received in 2019 and drawing a comparison by working out the percentage of the total member contribution that is given by the host country as the host premium contribution (Fig. 7).

Research Infrastructure	Host country	Host Premium Contribution (EUR)	Total member contributions in 2019 (EUR)	% host contribution of total membership
BBMRI	Austria	158,000	2,800,000	6
CESSDA	Norway	800,000	1,637,260	49
DARIAH	France	unknown	710,153	n/a
EATRIS	Netherlands	50,000	1,435,000	4
ECRIN	France	150,000	1,280,000	12
ECCSEL-ERIC	Norway	160,000	220,000	73
EMBRC	France	300,000	1,041,192	29
EMSO	Italy	220,000	500,000	44
EPOS	Italy	597,000	1,932,000	31
ESSsurvey	United Kingdom	764,000	2,700,000	28
EU-OPENSREEN	Germany	187,876	1,283,439	15
EURO-ARGO	France	unknown	340,000	n/a
ICOS	Finland	980,200	19,205,615	5
INSTRUCT	United Kingdom	104,040	919,020	11
Lifewatch	Spain	unknown	unknown	n/a
SHARE	Germany	10,000	380,050	3

Figure 7: % host premium contribution of total member contributions in RIs studied

By studying this data, the intention was to establish if countries with higher GDP per capita, and higher price level indices, gave more generous host premium contributions as part of their national contributions, than countries with lower economic results. In the following graphs, the data from the RIs, when the information was publicly available, is mapped against the GDP per capita for each host country (Fig. 8) and later against the price level indices for each country (Fig. 9).

Figure 8: % host premium contribution of total member contributions against GDP per capita

Figure 9: % host premium contribution of total member contributions against price level indices

Whilst there is some evidence to suggest that ERICs based in countries with higher GDP per capita rates offer comparatively higher host premium contributions, this is only applicable to Norway (CESSDA, ECCSEL-ERIC), which is not in the European Union. Otherwise, the overall trend seems to show that the countries with lower GDP/capita and price level index rates (Italy, France) are in fact more generous with host premium contributions than those with higher rates. Likewise, countries with higher GDP and price level indices will most likely have higher expenditure levels, and therefore these RIs may have greater outgoings.

This benchmarking exercise also studied the expenditure of the RIs, in order to estimate potential revenues and needs. Expenditure studies considered hub, service and project expenditures. Whilst the results were largely inconclusive, hub expenditure was the most obvious expense and the data showed almost every ERIC as having relatively high costs in this area. The benchmarking exercise, whilst a useful tool to map ESFRI landmark infrastructures has, ultimately shown that there are very few clear trends in the contribution models for research infrastructure. Therefore, it is possible to assume that DiSSCo should construct its revenue streams and partnerships based on its own specific needs, using this benchmark as a guide of what is realistic for a European ERIC.

4. Possible contribution models for the DiSSCo RI

As has become clear, there is no predefined contribution model for a RI and DiSSCo must formulate a model that meets its needs. DiSSCo should attract substantial revenue from national funds to achieve its ambition. This should be feasible, as some “countries may consider the vicinity of an RI a huge chance to stimulate high-end economic activity in their country/region” (Rizzuto *et al*) and so recurring revenue from national funders should ensure economic sustainability. One possible argument against this statement is the initial attractiveness of an RI for the economy of a country, but the eventual risk that the infrastructure and its activities cost more than the funds it generates. With this in mind, DiSSCo will need to find ways of generating new funds – from industry, partnerships, projects, etc. – in order to reduce its dependence on national funding.

As part of the work for this milestone, the team studied possible contribution models, for an AISBL and an ERIC, and carried out SWOT analyses to compare them. The work included the following comparisons:

- An AISBL contribution model involving only Natural History institutions. National funding is allocated directly to DiSSCo operators and revenue is pooled and redistributed by the central hub, but no funds are set aside for the functioning of the hub. This would be a simple next step from the current status quo and should ensure that natural history institutions remain very engaged. However, it may be difficult to obtain substantial revenue from national funds and attracting other disciplines is unlikely.
- An AISBL contribution model actively involving new stakeholders. The motivation behind this model is to attract new members from different disciplines and therefore encourage governments to invest more funds in the RI. Nevertheless, finding the most appropriate intermediary to liaise with different sectors could take time but, once established, this knowledge base could open doors for DiSSCo to respond to a greater number of project calls.

- An ERIC model with an emphasis on pooling money from new public stakeholders and obtaining revenue from new private/public stakeholders (Fig. 10). In this model, funds are allocated to the hub and revenue is transferred to DiSSCo operators. Service Level Agreements (SLAs) (including in-kind contributions) and other contractual models will be established between DiSSCo Operators and the DiSSCo Central hub. Depending on the level of financial commitment from the national funds and the level of the DiSSCo ambition, additional cash contributions from members may be required (Fig. 10).

Model 3: ERIC model

Figure 10: Possible ERIC contribution model

As outlined throughout this milestone, additional revenue for DiSSCo could be generated through the production of data for other stakeholders, outside of the taxonomy landscape. One weakness of this third model (Fig. 10) is that the needs of national history institutions could feel overlooked during the decision-making process. This is unlikely to occur however, as natural history institutions would remain at the core of the elaboration of the work programme and a decision that goes against their interests would be unlikely to be voted through.

5. Conclusion and next steps

This milestone has shown that DiSSCo has considerable freedom in the elaboration of a contribution model and that the RI will be able to function under several different options. The benchmarking exercise has shown that there is no generic model for European RIs. Nevertheless, this milestone argues that attracting other sectors, including private industry, to invest in DiSSCo, by enabling the production of data, could be a crucial revenue stream for the future RI.

This school of thought might be gathering speed in the Research Infrastructure landscape. As highlighted by milestone 8.4, “the ESFRI report also recommends that professional intermediaries, such as Industrial Liaison Officers and Industry Advisory Boards, should become common practice in RIs, including in the central hub of a distributed RI”. Likewise, the European

Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures notes that “dedicated initiatives can help increase knowledge and technology transfer from science to industry and public services and help driving innovation. In addition to acting as Users, industry also plays an increasing role in the construction, operation and innovation of Research Infrastructures” (European Commission). This being the case, future discussions around the contribution model might ask:

- How can DiSSCo attract new revenue streams?
- How feasible is it to expect revenue from other disciplines / sectors? And which disciplines / sectors?
- How do governments envisage to fund DiSSCo?
- Are governments ready to finance digitisation plans?
- How will national contributions be managed and coordinated, specifically within DiSSCo ERIC status?

In order to expand these discussions and to begin to lay the foundations of the DiSSCo contribution model, this milestone concludes that a task force, led by MNHN, will be set up. The task force will have as its aim to define the assumptions and hypotheses upon which the contribution model is based, as well as serving as a platform for a discussion around DiSSCo RI values, strategic objectives and programmes. The task force will most likely include representatives from all partners and will bring together part of the work of Work Packages 4, 7 and 8 specifically. Furthermore, the task force will try to establish if funding from other government departments, such as Health, Culture, Energy, etc., is a realistic ambition. Additional discussions will also be organised with tasks 4.2 and 4.4 in order to liaise on next steps regarding the exploration of possible industry collaborations. By doing so, it is hoped that the ideas put forward in this milestone can be backed up by evidence and that it will be possible to build a sustainable and ambitious contribution model for DiSSCo.

6. References

Rizutto C. *et al* (2013) Realising and Managing International Research Infrastructures (RAMIRI) Handbook. Accessed on 2021-05-04

Directorate General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), (2016) European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures. DOI: 10.2777/524573

Hrušák *et al* (2018) ESFRI Strategy Report on Research Infrastructures Roadmap 2018. ISBN PDF: 978-88-943243-3-4. Accessed on 2021-07-05